

THE CONCEPT OF "FAMILY" IN ENGLISH

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Annotation

The article is devoted to the consideration of the concept of "family" from the point of view of linguistics in the English language. In the English linguistic view, less attention paid to a group of people related by a commonality of interests, desires and requests. The concept of "family" is dominated by "pedigree by blood" and this meaning is directly connected in the UK with the concept of home as an impregnable fortress.

Key words

concept, family, linguistics, cognition, group of people, family from the English linguistic view.

Concept as a basic notion of cognitive linguistics

From birth, we, people, learn about the world around us, learn to remember the names of objects, compare them, comprehend the information received, try to master and analyze new knowledge, as well as reproduce everything that has been studied using the language. Therefore, we begin to develop basic knowledge. As a result, a person develops general concepts, which, subsequently, are combined into a system of knowledge about the world, consisting of concepts of varying degrees of complexity and abstraction.

The language units that a person uses during the thought process are concepts. They represent a general picture of the knowledge and experience gained as a result of a person's entire life and the result of the world he has mastered in the form of certain units, "quanta" of knowledge. It should be mentioned that people think and think in concepts, analyzing, comparing and combining concepts from different areas in mental activity. Man, as a result of thinking, form new concepts. The concept is also considered to be the exchange of any information, verbal or non-verbal, and the result of communication in general.

There are connections between concepts as units of mental activity - according to conceptual features [1]. The concept reflects the result of cognition. The national cognitive picture of the world is a general, stable, recurring in the pictures of the

world of individual representatives of the people [2]. A concept is an expedient, consistently meaningful concept that occurred as a result of theoretical knowledge. From this it follows that the difference between the concept and the concept depends on the discrepancy between theoretical and everyday knowledge - knowledge and cognition. Concepts, their formation and existence, does not depend on the language. Language is necessary for conveying a concept or thought and for discussion in the process of communication. Concepts need to be formulated, expressed in lexical units. The concept can be expressed in various language units: words, phrases, phraseological units, sentences and the whole text. It should be noted that there is such a thing as conceptual analysis, which refers to complex issues of linguistics. This concept is sometimes found under the name of cognitive analysis, but the concept of "conceptual analysis" is considered a more common option.

There is also such a concept as a conceptual metaphor, which means the connection of two names representing the main and additional subjects of the metaphor under study, which is a means through which it becomes possible to comprehend one phenomenon through the prism of another.

We have learned the basic meaning of the concept. Next, we will move on to a more detailed consideration of the concept of "family".

The concept of "family"

A family is a social group of individuals, consisting of two or more persons related by blood relationship, marriage or adoption, and having a need for union with each other. The distinguishing features of the family are mutual assistance, support, protection, joint life, the connectedness of the way of life of younger and older members of the family, a single economic basis, moral and emotional relationships, structure and norms of behavior.

Currently, there are a large number of different types of families:

a) Big family. A few decades ago, it was quite common to meet family and relatives living in the same house. Aunts, uncles, grandparents helped with the care of the child and gave advice on how to raise. This approach has been very helpful, especially for young families who have struggled with many of the challenges of raising children. Today, a large family is the exception rather than the rule.

b) Divorced and incomplete families. National statistics show that 25% of children under the age of 18 live in single parent families. In most cases, the missing parent is the father. Single-parent families headed by mothers are much more likely to live at or below the poverty level.

c) Mixed families. Divorce, as mentioned earlier, is not new. It leaves small

children without a parent and creates a lot of tension for everyone involved. Blended families create problems for both parents and children.

d) Same-sex families. A small but growing number of children in America have either two moms or two dads. In some cases, these children were born into heterosexual families, which were subsequently divorced when one of the partners discovered his homosexual inclinations. Others were either adopted or artificially born.

The family of the future seems to have a very different meaning. However, if you look closely, the original concept of the family is preserved. The family is what everyone aspires to; the family implies friendships and living together.

Family from the point of view of english and russian linguistics

A large number of English lexical and phraseological units have full or partial equivalents in the Russian language, which is explained by the coincidence of the mental representation of reality among the speakers of these languages and common elements of culture - the so-called "cultural universals". includes figurative scenarios of situations, events, facts typical for a given culture.

The subject of our analysis was the linguistic means of designating the concept of "family" in Russian and English linguistic cultures. First of all, the system of meanings of the noun "family" was considered:

- a group of close relatives (husband, wife, parents, children) living together;
- a group of animals, birds, consisting of a male, one or more females and cubs (family of sparrows, family of lions);
- a group of related languages united by a common origin (family of Slavic languages);
- clan, generation [3].

By analogy with the analysis of the system of meanings of the noun "family" in Russian, the analysis of the meanings of the noun "family" in English was carried out:

- parents and their children;
- a group of persons related by blood or marriage;
- the members of the household;
- a group of things with common characteristics;
- biol. A group of related plants or animals ranking between a genus and an order [4].

The analysis of dictionary interpretations of lexical units with the meaning "family" showed that they coincide in the following definitions:

1. a group of people who are related to each other, especially parents and their

children ;

2. a group of related animals, plants, languages etc. [5].

Comparing dictionary interpretations of lexical units with the meaning of "family" in Russian and English, we can conclude that in English the noun family has a much greater number of interpretations than in Russian, and has a meaning that is not inherent in this word in Russian: the children of the same parents.

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